

The Relation Between Intensity and Velocity of Photo-Chemical Reactions

W. V. BHAGWAT

Holkar College, Indore

The relationship between intensity and velocity of a photochemical reaction can vary from direct to square-root. For reactions in which the primary process directly gives rise to final products, the extent of activation determines the relationship. If there is a chain mechanism, the order of the reaction with respect to chain carriers in the chain termination stage determines this relationship [and not the total molecularity of this stage]. If the molecularity with respect to chain carriers is unity, the direct relationship between intensity and velocity is likely to exist. If the order with respect to chain carriers is bimolecular square-root relationship is likely to be observed. By varying intensity and concentrations and the nature of reactants [over a wide range], the same reaction may be made to show a relationship extending from direct to square-root.

BHATTACHARYA and Dhar¹ classified photo-chemical reactions into the following three groups :

- (i) The reactions in which the velocity tends to be directly proportional to the square-root of the intensity.
- (ii) The reactions in which the velocity tends to be directly proportional to the intensity.
- (iii) The reactions in which the velocity tends to be proportional to the square of the intensity.

Bhagwat² and Bhagwat and Dhar³ deduced a theoretical expression for the relation between intensity and velocity of photo-chemical reactions from the view point of activation. If the intensity is varied in 'n' equal stages, and 'A' is the total number of molecules, 'x' the number of active molecules originally present before exposure, and 'y' is the fraction of inactive molecules activated each time by exposure, the photo-chemical acceleration in the first stage is proportional to $(A-n)y$ and in the 'n'th stage it is proportional to $(A-x)[1-(1-y)^n]$.

It is evident from above, that 'y' becomes very small, if photo-chemical acceleration over the dark reaction is very small. Moreover 'y' is a fraction less than unity. Hence, higher powers of 'y' in the expansion of $(1-y)^n$ as square etc may be neglected. The photo-chemical acceleration in the 'n'th stage is therefore proportional to

$$(A-x)[1-(1-ny)] \text{ or } n(A-x)y$$

Hence, when the photo-chemical acceleration is in the 'n'th stage or when the intensity is increased n fold, the acceleration is n times the acceleration in the first stage. Thus, when the photo-chemical acceleration is small, the velocity is directly proportional to the intensity. However, higher powers of y cannot be neglected when y is large and hence the velocity-intensity relation is less than unity or approaches square-root relationship.

Thus, when the absorption of the radiation is higher and the reaction is not markedly photo-chemical in nature and the velocity of the reaction in the dark is appreciable, direct proportionality is likely to be observed. On the other hand when the reaction is highly photo-chemical in nature and the velocity of the dark reaction is practically negligible, square-root relationship is to be expected.

The above theoretical expression brings out the important fact that the relation between intensity and velocity can never exceed unity. In other words, the square relationship suggested by Bhattacharya and Dhar¹ is not possible.

Practically in all cases the observed relationship is either unity or less than unity. The only peculiar case is that observed by Baly and Barker⁴ with the photo-chemical combination of hydrogen and chlorine, where a relationship greater than unity was observed. Bhattacharya and Dhar¹ also observed such a relationship in a few cases where special attempts were made to reduce the photo-chemical acceleration by adding such inhibitors as potassium bromide or potassium iodide. These deviations were explained by us on the ground that in initial stages, part of light energy absorbed is used in destroying the inhibitors and the whole absorbed energy is not responsible for the photo-chemical reaction. When intensity is increased the proportionate loss of energy in destroying the inhibitors becomes smaller and smaller and hence apparently it appears that the rate of the photo-chemical reaction is proportional to a power of intensity greater than unity. Baly and Barker⁴ admitted that their reacting gases were impure.

Thus the relationship between intensity and velocity could be one or less than one only.

The above discussion is applicable to cases where the primary process directly results into the final products of the reaction.

Our views of the photo-chemical reactions with chain mechanism are to be modified. It seems that in these cases the relationship between intensity and velocity is guided by the chain terminating reaction. This will be clear from the following examples.

(i) In case of photo-chemical oxidation of acetaldehyde studied by Bowen and Tietze⁵ the mechanism suggested is

A represents acetaldehyde and AO_2 the oxidation product. The chain terminating reaction is,

The rate of reaction on the basis of this mechanism is given by

$$\frac{d[AO_2]}{dt} = K\sqrt{I}[A] \quad \dots (i)$$

or the velocity of the photo-chemical reaction is proportional to the square root of the intensity.

(ii) Similarly for the photo-chemical reaction between hydrogen and bromine, Bodenstein and Lütkeymeyer⁶ suggested the mechanism.

The rate of reaction by this mechanism is given by

$$\frac{d[HBr]}{dt} = \frac{K\sqrt{I}[H_2][Br_2]}{K_1[Br_2] + [HBr]} \quad \dots (ii)$$

This holds for constant pressure.

In this case the velocity of the photo-chemical reaction is proportional to the square root of the intensity. If the chains terminate at walls as

the rate of the reaction is given by

$$\frac{d[HBr]}{dt} = \frac{4I[H_2]}{K_s \left\{ 1 + \frac{K_3[HBr]}{K_4[Br_2]} \right\}} \quad \dots (iii)$$

and the velocity of the reaction is now directly proportional to the intensity.

(iii) In case of the photo-chemical reaction between hydrogen and chlorine free from oxygen, the mechanism as suggested by Norrish and Richie⁶ is

and the rate of the reaction is given by

$$\frac{d[HCl]}{dt} = \frac{2K_2 K_3 \sqrt{K_1/K_4} [H_2] [Cl_2] \sqrt{I}}{K_5 [Cl_2] + K_6 [HCl]} \quad \dots (iv)$$

Thus the rate of the reaction is proportional to the square root of intensity.

(iv) The mechanism suggested by Lender and Rolletson⁹ for the photo-chemical formation of phosgene is,

The rate of the reaction is given by

$$\frac{d[COCl_2]}{dt} = k\sqrt{I}[CO][Cl_2] \quad \dots (v)$$

or the velocity of the reaction is proportional to the square root of the intensity.

It will be clear from these observations that in cases (i), (ii), (iv) and (v) where the chains terminate bimolecularly, the rate of the reaction is proportional to the square root of the intensity, while it is directly proportional to the intensity where the chains terminate unimolecularly as in the case (iii). Thus if concentration of the radicals is high, bimolecular termination in the gas phase is favoured, while for low concentration, the termination is more likely to occur unimolecularly at the wall and the direct relationship between velocity and intensity is likely to be observed. By changing intensity and concentration of the reactants over a wide range it is possible to get relationship from direct to square root for the same reaction.

The above statement needs modification. Consider the following chain reactions and their chain termination process.

(i) The chain termination in case of oxidation of aldehydes in presence of alcohol is bimolecular⁸ as

$AO_2^* + X(\text{alcohol}) \dots$ chain termination... (A)
but the rate of the reaction is given by

$$\frac{d[AO_2]}{dt} = \frac{K^1[A]I}{[X]}$$

or there is direct proportionality between intensity and velocity of the reaction.

(ii) Similarly in case of hydrogen chlorine reaction in presence of oxygen the chains terminate bimolecularly as

But the rate of the reaction is given by¹⁰

$$\frac{d[HCl]}{dt} = \frac{K I [Cl_2]}{[O_2]}$$

and

$$\frac{d[HCl]}{dt} = \frac{4 K_2 K_3 I [H_2] [Cl_2]}{[O_2] (K_2 K_4 [H_2] + K_3 K_5 [Cl_2])}$$

or the velocity is directly proportional to intensity.

(iii) The behaviour of $H_2 + Br_2$ reaction at varying pressure is similar. Here the chains terminate as

where X is any molecular species present which removes energy. The reaction is termolecular and the rate of the reaction is given by¹¹

$$\frac{d[HBr]}{dt} = \frac{k\sqrt{I}[X][H_2][Br_2]}{K_1[Br_2] + [HBr]}$$

or square root relationship exists between intensity and velocity and not $I^{1/2}$ relationship, though the reaction is termolecular.

The above discussion will make it clear that it is not the total molecularity of chain reaction that determines the relationship between intensity and velocity if we consider the chain terminating processes discussed above,

We observe that [X] or [O₂] are not chain carriers. In case v, both COCl and Cl are chain carriers, though they are different. Thus it is the molecularity with respect to chain carriers that is significant in determining the relationship between velocity and intensity of a particular photochemical process and not the total molecularity of the chain terminating reaction. Thus the reactions (A), (B) and (C), though bimolecular as a whole, are unimolecular with respect to chain carrier and hence direct relationship between intensity and velocity is observed. The reaction (D) as a whole is termolecular but is bimolecular with respect to chain

carrier. Hence the square root relationship between intensity and velocity exists.

Acknowledgement

This investigation was taken up by the author in the University of Allahabad under the guidance of Prof. N. R. Dhar.

References

1. A. K. BHATTACHARYA and N. R. DHAR, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 6, 493.
2. W. V. BHAGWAT, *U. P. Akad. Sci.*, 1933, 1, 54.
3. W. V. BHAGWAT and N. R. DHAR, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1931, 199, 406.
4. Baly and Barker, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, 119, 658.
5. Bowen and Tietze, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 137, 234.
6. M. Bodenstein and H. Lütke Meyer, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1924, 114, 208.
7. J. G. Calvert and J. N. Pitts, "Photochemistry", John Wiley and Sons, 1966, p. 51.
8. R. G. W. Norrish and H. Ritchie, *Proc. Roy. Soc. A*, 1933, 140, 713.
9. Lender and G. K. Rolletson, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 52, 500.
10. M. Bodenstein and Dun, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1913, 85, 297.
11. Thon, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1926, 124, 227.
12. Josi, *Z. physikal. Chem. B*, 1929, 3, 95.